

Monitoring of buckling behaviors of VaRTM stiffened panel using FBG sensors

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SUMMARY

FBG (Fiber Bragg Grating) sensors were embedded into the CFRP stiffened panel during VaRTM (Vacuum-assisted Resin Transfer Molding) process. The buckling behaviour was investigated under compressive loading for the intact panel. The signal changes of the FBG sensor could detect the buckling behavior until the final failures of the panels.

Keywords: Health Monitoring, Fiber-optic sensors, CFRP, VaRTM, Buckling

INTRODUCTION

Fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors are candidates for the damage sensing devices because they have the advantages such as high sensitivity to strain and capability of multiplexing. The reflection spectrum from the FBG sensor is known to be sensitive to non-uniform strain distribution along the entire length of the grating [1]. Hence the FBG sensor had been applied to the monitoring of delamination growth in CFRP laminates since the strain distribution is changed by the internal damages [2-3]. These results show that the FBG sensor can evaluate strain and temperature as well as matrix cracks [4], delamination [2-3], and residual strain after molding [5]. However, there are few reports about monitoring of strain and damage growth under compressive loading condition. In the present paper, the FBG sensors were applied to the compressive loading test of the CFRP stiffened panel fabricated by VaRTM (Vacuum-assisted Resin Transfer Molding) process. The VaRTM is one of integral molding technology for composite structures.

FABRICATION OF CFRP STIFFENED PANEL

As shown in Fig. 1, the test panel was fabricated by KADO Corporation, assuming a portion of the fuselage structure or secondary airframe of small size aircraft. The panel has two thin skin bays with three T-shape stringers and evaluation area is length of 360mm x width of 350mm. The VaRTM technique was adopted for the fabrication of the panel. The stacking sequences of skin and stringer were $[(+45/-45)(0/90)]_s$ and $[(+45/-45)(0/90)]_{2s}$, respectively. Stringers and thin panel were made of aerospace-grade carbon fiber Non Crimp Fabric (NCF). They were fabricated separately and then the pre-formed stringers were put on the stacked skin.

FBG sensors (Neutron Co., Ltd.) were embedded into an interface between the skin and the stringer. The FBG sensor was fabricated in a single optical fiber as a localized sensor, and its gauge length was 10mm. Fig. 2 showed the setup of the dry fabric and embedded FBG sensors before resin flow process. The resin was impregnated into the vacuum bag including the combined dry preforms and molding equipments at 40°C. After the confirmation of the impregnation, the resin was stored at 80°C in 6hours for the curing process. The post-curing was carried out at 120°C in 3hours.

Fig. 1 Dimensions of stiffened panel.

Fig. 2 Setup of dry fabric and FBG sensors.

STRAIN CALIBRATION OF FBG SENSORS

FBG sensors have a periodic variation in the refractive index along a certain length of a single-mode optical fiber. When a broadband light is launched into the FBG sensor, a narrowband light is reflected due to Bragg diffraction. Though the relationship between the wavelength of the reflected light and applied strain is found to be almost linear [6], it is difficult to calculate the absolute value of the strain using optical parameters of the FBG sensors. Therefore, the calibration test was carried out before the monitoring of the stiffened panel under compressive loading.

The FBG sensor and the electric strain gage were attached to the surface of an aluminium square bar by strain gage cement as shown in Fig. 3. The gage length of the strain gage is 5mm. The bar size is 10mm x 10mm x 200mm. The tensile loading was applied to the bar under constant displacement control of 1 mm/min. The wavelengths of the reflected light were measured by spectrum analyzer when the loading was stopped at pre-determined strain values.

Fig. 4 shows the relationship between the wavelength of the reflected light and the strain measured by the strain gage. The wavelength of $0\mu\epsilon$ is different from the wavelength in strain-free state because the wavelength is shifted by the surface bonding to the bar. Thus the regression line is calculated using results of from $50\mu\epsilon$ to $1000\mu\epsilon$, and shift keeping its inclination. The modified regression line was expressed by

$$\lambda = 1549.57 + 0.001184 \cdot \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where λ (nm) and ε ($\mu\epsilon$) are wavelength of the reflected light and the calculated strain, respectively. For example, the experimentally-inferred elongation of the FBG sensor was $617\mu\epsilon$ due to the adhesion to the surface of the bar. The residual strain and/or stress

can be estimated by the relationship between wavelength and strain. In this study, the equation (1) was used for the evaluation of strain in the FBG sensors.

Fig. 3 Dimensions of stiffened panel. Fig. 4 Relation between wavelength and strain.

MONITORING OF STIFFENED PANEL

Strain survey tests

The six FBG sensors were embedded into the panel during the VaRTM process. The strain gages were bonded to the surface of the panel after aluminum fixtures were attached to both ends of the panel by potting epoxy resin. The arrangement of the FBG sensors and the strain gages are summarized in Fig. 5. Unfortunately, the test results can be measured only four FBG sensors because the other two FBG sensors were broken at the root of the sensor line. Fig. 6 shows the photograph of the stiffened panel.

Fig. 5 Locations of FBGs and strain gages. Fig. 6 Photograph of the stiffened panel.

The compressive loading was applied by a screw-driven testing machine, INSTRON 5589, under displacement control. During the test, out-of-plane displacement of the skin panel was observed by optical 3D measurement system ARAMIS and buckling behavior of the panel was evaluated. The results of strain measurement are shown in Fig. 7. All the FBGs have the compressive strain under the 0kN because the panel is cooling down from cure temperature to room temperature. The estimated residual strains measured by the FBGs were summarized in Table 1. Though the influence of location on the residual strain could not be observed, the residual strain interface between the skin part and the stringer part could be estimated about from -100 to $-250\mu\epsilon$. The strain-load curves were almost linear till 40kN compressive loading because the global buckling did not occur. This behaviour could be confirmed by the measurement of out-of-plane displacement of the skin panel. Fig. 8 shows out-of-plane displacement of the skin panel taken by the ARAMIS, where the color contour plots indicate the level of out-of-displacement. In this study, the first buckling occurred at 40kN and buckling mode is a global one half-wave at center of the panel (Fig. 8(b)). The buckling mode changed to five half-waves at each skin at 50kN (Fig. 8(c)). Finally, stringer webs started to buckle (i.e. crippling occurred) and the skin bay buckling mode changed to six half-waves (Fig. 8(d) and (e)).

Table 1 Estimated residual strains

	FBG1	FBG2	FBG3	FBG4
Residual Strains ($\mu\epsilon$)	-143.5	-236.4	-228.0	-118.2

Fig. 7 Strain-Load curves measured by FBGs.

Fig. 8 Contour plots of out-of-plane displacement of the skin panel.

The results of strain gages, FB1 - FB4 (see in Fig. 5) corresponding to location of the FBG sensors are shown in Fig. 9 (a). The first buckling could be also confirmed by the nonlinear behaviour of the strain changes. After nonlinear behavior was started, there were opposite changes between the strains measured in FBGs and the strains measured in strain gages. For example, when the compressive strain of the FBG2 was increased, the compressive strain of the FB2 was decreased due to the buckling. That is because that the neutral axis of the panel is located within the flange part. The results of strain gages, SK1 – SK8 (see in Fig. 5) are shown in Fig. 9 (b). The SK1 – SK4 and SK5 – SK8 were attached to the stringer side and the skin side, respectively. The drastic strain changes showed the second and third buckling which started at 53.8kN and 59.8kN, respectively. The embedded FBG sensors could be detected the first buckling (40kN) and the third buckling (59.8kN).

(a) FB series of gages corresponding to FBGs (b) SK series of gages on the skin

Fig. 9 Strain-Load curves measured by strain gages from 0kN to 100kN.

Compressive failure tests

After the strain survey tests, the compressive loading was applied to the panel till final failure. The results of strain measurement under compressive loading are shown in Fig. 10. Using equation (1), the strains were calculated by the center wavelength of the spectrum.

Fig. 10 Strain-Load curves measured by FBGs from 0kN to 180kN.

Though the spectrum has one peak when the strain of the FBG sensors is almost uniform, the shape of spectrum is distorted due to debonding and/or damages [7]. Since the strain change due to the buckling is small, it predicts that the drastic strain change of the FBG3 was caused by the debonding between the skin and the flange part. Fig. 11 shows the measured spectrum of the FBG3 during compressive loading.

Fig. 11 Measured spectra of FBG3 during from 0kN to 180kN.

Though the spectrum was shifted keeping its shape during from 0kN to 120kN, the distortion of the spectrum shape indicated the non-uniform strain during from 0kN to 180kN. This behavior was confirmed by the results of strain gages, FB1 - FB4 as shown in Fig. 11 (a). After nonlinear behavior was started, opposite change between the strains measured FBGs and the strains measured strain gages was also observed till final failure. On the other hand, the results of the SK series gages (see in Fig. 11(b)) showed the opposite change due to the global buckling because there were no debondings in the skin part. As a result, the strain gages of the flange (FB series) only indicated the debonding because the stiffness of the flange part is large compare with that of the skin for such a thin skin panel. The strain gages of the skin (SK series) only indicated the mode change.

(a) FB series of gages corresponding to FBGs (b) SK series of gages on the skin

Fig. 11 Strain-Load curves measured by strain gages from 0 kN to final failure.

When the final failure occurred, the FBG2 and FBG4 were presumed to break in the panel because the reflected light could not be measured. Fig. 12 shows the photographs of the panel around the FBGs after the final failure. Though the large damage could not be observed around the FBG1, there was debonding around the FBG3. The final failure occurred at the debonding around the center stringer where the FBG3 was embedded.

Fig. 12 Photographs of the panel around the FBGs after the final failure.

CONCLUSIONS

The buckling behavior and debonding was detected by using embedded FBG sensors. The estimated results could be confirmed by the results of the strain gages and the optical 3D measurement system. The residual strain interface between the skin part and stringer parts could be estimated about from -100 to -250 $\mu\epsilon$. As a result, not only the residual strain of the composite panel but the mode change of the composite panel could be evaluated easily by the present method using FBG sensor.

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